

GRID DIFFRACTION EFFECTS

L. Lindgren 79-09-19 ESTEC

1. A (more) rigorous expression for the intensity at the collecting aperture of the relay optics

Let $a(x, y)$ be the complex amplitude of light at the telescope entrance pupil. $a(x, y) \equiv 0$ outside the pupil, and inside the pupil we may put $a(x, y) = 1$ for the ideal instrument. However, the influence of aberrations may be studied by putting $a(x, y) = e^{-ik\varphi(x, y)}$, where $\varphi(x, y)$ is the wavefront error (delay). For instance, defocussing may be introduced with $\varphi(x, y) \propto x^2 + y^2$.

For the time being, only the ideal instrument has been studied in detail. [$\varphi(x, y) \equiv 0$]. $k = 2\pi/\lambda$.

In the image plane the angular distribution of the complex amplitude is given by the FT of $a(x, y)$, viz.

$$A(p, q) = \iint a(x, y) \exp[-ik(px + qy)] dx dy \quad (1)$$

(disregarding normalization factors of type $k/2\pi$ etc.).

(p, q) are angular coordinates counted from the geometrical image centre (radians).

In the absence of a grid, the light would propagate behind the focal surface, and a field lens near the focal surface would image the telescope entrance pupil

(2)

on the collecting lens of the relay optics. This imaging is formally expressed by the FT

$$b(x, y) = \iint A(p, q) \exp[-ik(px + qy)] dp dq, \quad (2)$$

where (x, y) are linear coordinates corresponding to those in the pupil plane (only adjusted for demagnification). From the Fourier Theorem we find (apart from constant factor)

$$b(x, y) \equiv a(-x, -y), \quad (3)$$

i.e. the entrance pupil is imaged without distortion, but rotated 180° as a result of the crossing of light rays at the telescope focal plane.

The intensities at the entrance pupil, focal surface, and relay optics collecting lens (hereafter referred to as "collecting lens") are of course given by $|a(x, y)|^2$, $|A(p, q)|^2$, and $|b(x, y)|^2$ respectively, and the conservation of energy $\iint |a|^2 dx dy = \iint |A|^2 dp dq = \iint |b|^2 dx dy$ follows from Parseval's Theorem.

Now we may introduce an arbitrary grid with (complex) amplitude transmittance $R(p, q)$ at the focal surface

~~... the complex amplitude immediately behind the grid is~~

modified complex amplitude immediately behind the grid is

$$\tilde{A}(p, q) \equiv A(p, q) R(p, q), \quad (4)$$

and the modified amplitude at the collecting lens is

$$\tilde{b}(x, y) = \iint A(p, q) R(p, q) \exp[-ik(px + qy)] dp dq \quad (5) \quad \textcircled{2}$$

Introducing the FT of $R(p, q)$:

$$r(x, y) \equiv \iint R(p, q) \exp[-ik(px + qy)] dp dq \quad (6)$$

we find

$$\tilde{b}(x, y) = b(x, y) \otimes r(x, y) \quad (7)$$

$$= a(-x, -y) \otimes r(x, y) \quad (7a)$$

where $\otimes$ denotes convolution.

For a rectangular periodic grid (slits normal to x axis)

$$R(p, q) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |p - p_0 - ns| < s\delta/2 \text{ for some } n; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where s is the grid period, $s\delta$ the slit width ($\delta = \text{grid ratio}$), p_0 the position of the grid centre, and $n = \text{integer}$.

It is convenient to assume that scanning is performed by varying p_0 rather than the object direction. The FT of (8) is

$$r(x, y) = \Delta(y) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(n\pi\delta)}{n\pi} \Delta(x - n\lambda/s) e^{-i2\pi n p_0/s} \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac function. Performing the convolution (7)

we find

$$\tilde{b}(x, y) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(n\pi\delta)}{n\pi} e^{-i2\pi n p_0/s} b(x - n\lambda/s, y). \quad (10)$$

The intensity at (x, y) on the collecting lens is

$$I(x, y) \equiv |\tilde{b}(x, y)|^2 = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(n\pi\delta)}{n\pi} \frac{\sin(m\pi\delta)}{m\pi} e^{-i2\pi(n-m)p_0/s} \times b(x-n\lambda/s, y) b^*(x-m\lambda/s, y) \quad (11)$$

Putting $n-m = l$, the summation can be written

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i2\pi l p_0/s} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(n\pi\delta)}{n\pi} \frac{\sin[(n-l)\pi\delta]}{(n-l)\pi} b(x-\frac{n\lambda}{s}, y) b^*(x-\frac{n\lambda}{s} + \frac{l\lambda}{s}, y) \\ = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} E_l(x, y) e^{-i2\pi l p_0/s}, \quad (12)$$

where the l th harmonic of the intensity variation at (x, y) is

$$E_l(x, y) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(n\pi\delta)}{n\pi} \frac{\sin[(n-l)\pi\delta]}{(n-l)\pi} b(x-\frac{n\lambda}{s}, y) b^*(x-\frac{n\lambda}{s} + \frac{l\lambda}{s}, y) \quad (13)$$

We notice that (13) can be integrated with respect to y by introducing the function

$$F(x, \xi) \equiv \int b(x, y) b^*(x + \xi, y) dy, \quad (14)$$

yielding

$$E_l(x) \equiv \int E_l(x, y) dy = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n c_{n-l} F(x - \frac{n\lambda}{s}, \frac{l\lambda}{s}) \quad (15)$$

where $c_n \equiv \sin(n\pi\delta)/(n\pi)$. (16)

The integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(x, \xi) dx$ is obviously the autocorrelation function of $b(x, y)$ with displacement $(\xi, 0)$, i.e. the complex OTF at spatial frequency $(\xi, 0)$, $T(\xi)$. Integrating (15) with infinite bounds (no restriction on

the collecting efficiency of the relay optics) we obtain

(5)

$$E_l \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_l(x) dx = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n c_{n-l} T\left(\frac{l\lambda}{s}\right). \quad (17)$$

Now it can be shown that

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n c_{n-l} = c_l i \quad (18)$$

hence (17) reduces to the well-known expression

$$E_l = c_l T\left(\frac{l\lambda}{s}\right). \quad (19)$$

For a restricted collection efficiency we should compute

$$E'_l \equiv \int_{x_1}^{x_2} E_l(x) dx \quad (20)$$

where, for instance, $-x_1 = x_2 = \beta D/2$, β being the oversizing factor and D the length of the telescope entrance pupil.

2. First numerical example: ideal telescope with rectangular pupil and no central obstruction.

For ease of calculation, consider first an aberration-free instrument with rectangular entrance pupil (length D) and no central obstruction. Thus, $F(x, \xi)$ is found to be

$$F(x, \xi) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |x| < D/2 \text{ and } |x+\xi| < D/2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

This is illustrated in the diagram below; $F(x, z)$ is unity in the hatched area.

Fig.1.

For illustration we may take $D = 0.25 \text{ m}$, $\delta = 0.25$, $s = 1.1$, $\lambda = 444 \text{ nm}$, which gives very nearly $\lambda/s = D/3$. Thus, we need only consider $l = -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$, corresponding to $z = -\frac{2}{3}D, -\frac{1}{3}D, 0, \frac{1}{3}D, \frac{2}{3}D$.

(dashed line in figure above). Given a particular harmonic (l) and position on the collecting lens (x), we see easily from the diagram which terms (n) should be included in the summation, eq. (15). For instance, for $l=1$ and $x = 1.25 \frac{D}{2}$, the two terms $n=2$ and $n=3$ should be included, i.e.

$$E_1(1.25 \frac{D}{2}) = C_2 C_1 + C_3 C_2. \quad (22)$$

For $l=-1$ and same x , we find $n=1$ and $n=2$, i.e.

$$E_{-1}(1.25 \frac{D}{2}) = c_1 c_2 + c_2 c_3 = E_1(1.25 \frac{D}{2}). \quad (23)$$

With no aberrations we have in general $E_{-l}(x) \equiv E_l(x)$, so that the l :th modulation factor at point x is

$$M_l = \frac{E_{-l}(x) + E_l(x)}{E_0(x)} = 2 E_l(x) / E_0(x). \quad (24)$$

For $\delta = 0.25$ we compute easily the following table.

Table 1.

$ x $ (units of $\frac{D}{2}$)	$E_0(x)$	$2E_1(x)$	$2E_2(x)$	$M_1(x)$	$M_2(x)$
$0 < x < \frac{1}{3}$	.163821	.225079	.101321	1.373933	.618487
$\frac{1}{3} < x < 1$	.138491	.184184	.079547	1.329938	.574604
$1 < x < 1\frac{2}{3}$	.081620	.095527	-.033774	1.170381	.413792
$1\frac{2}{3} < x < 2\frac{1}{3}$	.030959	.023882	.000000	0.771395	.000000
$2\frac{1}{3} < x < 3$	.007655	.000000	-.006755	0.000000	-.882397
$3 < x < 3\frac{2}{3}$	.004841	.004776	.000000	0.986640	.000000
$3\frac{2}{3} < x < 4\frac{1}{3}$	.005875	.008188	.002895	1.393700	.492747
$4\frac{1}{3} < x < 5$	.003848	.003412	.000000	0.886606	.000000
$5 < x < 5\frac{2}{3}$	.001659	.000000	-.001608	0.000000	-.969423
$5\frac{2}{3} < x < 6\frac{1}{3}$	.001639	.001592	.000000	0.971390	.000000
$6\frac{1}{3} < x < 7$	.002057	.002895	.001023	1.407265	.497543
$\int_0^7 (-) dx$	.240370	.291330	.106378	1.212008	.442559
$\int_0^\infty (-) dx$	.250000	.300105	.106103	1.200422	.424413

The last line but one gives the integrals of E_0 , $2E_1$, and $2E_2$ over $x \in [0, 7]$ (the integration is exact since the integrands are constant within each interval of x). The last line gives the total integrals $x \in [0, \infty]$ according to (19), noting that $T(\frac{2}{3}) = 1 - 1/3$.

The table shows some extremely interesting results: although the regions outside the geometrical image of the entrance pupil ($|x| > D/2$) contains much light, the modulated light components E_1 and E_2 fall off much faster with increasing $|x|$. This is shown by the decreasing modulation factors M_1, M_2 . This will surely compensate for the loss of photons.

Let us evaluate this effect. The photonstatistical mean error σ of the timing of a Poisson process with intensity $I(t) = I_0 [1 + M_1 \cos \omega t + M_2 \cos 2\omega t]$ is proportional to

$$\sigma_0 \equiv \left\{ I_0 \left\langle \frac{(M_1 \sin \omega t + 2M_2 \sin 2\omega t)^2}{1 + M_1 \cos \omega t + M_2 \cos 2\omega t} \right\rangle \right\}^{-1/2} \quad (25)$$

where the average $\langle \rangle$ may be evaluated over one modulation period. For $M_2 = 0$ (25) reduces to the well-known formula

$$\sigma_0 = \left\{ I_0 [1 - \sqrt{1 - M_1^2}] \right\}^{-1/2}, \quad (26)$$

but for the general case $M_2 \neq 0$ no simple formula for the average has been found. However, the average is quite easily evaluated by numerical methods. Alternatively, a more conservative mean error may be derived from Fourier analysis of the photon counts; one finds in this case the simple expression

$$\sigma_0' = \left\{ I_0 \frac{M_1^2}{2 - M_2} \right\}^{-1/2} \geq \sigma_0 \quad (27)$$

By means of the preceding table we derive easily, as a function of the collecting lens oversizing factor $\beta = \frac{|x|_{max}}{D/2}$ the quantities

$$E_0 = I_0 = \int_0^{\beta} E_0(x) dx \quad (\text{average intensity}) \quad (28) \quad (9)$$

$$M_L = \frac{\int_0^{\beta} 2E_L(x) dx}{\int_0^{\beta} E_0(x) dx} \quad (\text{modulation factors}) \quad (29)$$

from which σ_0 and σ_0' are then computed. The results are shown in the Figure below.

The important result is that with moderate or even no oversizing ($\beta = 1 - 1.5$), the astrometric weight of the collected light is already larger than for the "ideal" relay optics ($\beta = \infty$), in spite of the fact that only 60-75% of the energy is transmitted. Thus, the intensity collection efficiency alone is not very relevant for the optimisation.

Table 1a

Unobstructed pupil $\lambda 444 \text{ nm}$

9.5

$x_{\text{max}} (\beta)$	E_0	$2E_1$	$2E_2$	M_1	M_2	σ_0	σ_0'
0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-
1/3	.054607	.075026	.033774	1.373933	0.618486	2.720666	3.660902
2/3	.100771	.136421	.060299	1.353777	0.598382	2.246183	2.754867
1	.146934	.197816	.086825	1.346286	0.590910	1.902101	2.300225
1 1/3	.174141	.229658	.098083	1.318805	0.563239	1.869629	2.178017
1 2/3	.201348	.261500	.109341	1.298750	0.543046	1.813764	2.071209
2	.211667	.269461	.109341	1.273040	0.516570	1.860073	2.079527
2 1/3	.221987	.277422	.109341	1.249720	0.492556	1.895360	2.085182
2 2/3	.224539	.277422	.107089	1.235518	0.476930	1.934065	2.107973
3	.227090	.277422	.104838	1.221636	0.461656	1.971309	2.130520
3 1/3	.230318	.280606	.104838	1.218342	0.455187	1.973955	2.125715
4 1/3	.234234	.286064	.106768	1.221274	0.455816	1.952034	2.102380
5	.236800	.288339	.106768	1.217650	0.450878	1.955383	2.100535
7	.240370	.291330	.106378	1.212008	0.442559	1.963486	2.100198
∞	.250000	.300105	.106107	1.200422	0.424413	1.972366	2.091304

3. Effect of central pupil obstruction

It is important to see if the conclusions of the preceding section are still valid (a) with a central obstruction of the telescope entrance pupil, (b) with polychromatic light, and (c) in the presence of small aberrations, in particular defocussing. We consider first the effect of the central pupil obstruction. A linear obscuration factor of $\eta = 0.45$ is assumed. The pupil function $v(x, y)$ is shown below.

$v(x, y)$ is unity in the hatched region. [For simplicity, x is normalized to unity at the edge of the pupil: $x := x / (D/2)$] The function $F(x, \xi)$ is again zero outside a rhomboid in the (x, ξ) plane; inside the rhomboid the function is either 1 (normalized) or $1 - \eta = 0.55$. See figure on next page.

Assuming $\lambda = 444 \text{ nm}$ ($\lambda/s = 2/3$) and $\delta = 0.25$ we find the values for the harmonic components in Table 2.

Fig. 4

Table 2.

$ x $	$E_0(x)$	$2E_1(x)$	$2E_2(x)$	$M_1(x)$	$M_L(x)$
$0 < x < \frac{13}{60}$	0.135696	.123793	.101321	.912286	.746678
$\frac{13}{60} < x < \frac{20}{60}$	0.112899	.123793	.055727	1.096493	.493597
$\frac{20}{60} < x < \frac{27}{60}$	0.087569	.101301	.043768	1.156819	.499807
$\frac{27}{60} < x < \frac{53}{60}$	0.115694	.101301	.079577	.875594	.687827
$\frac{53}{60} < x < \frac{60}{60}$	0.104295	.101301	.043768	.971293	.419656
$\frac{60}{60} < x < \frac{67}{60}$	0.047424	.052540	.018576	1.107869	.391691
$\frac{67}{60} < x < \frac{93}{60}$	0.070221	.052540	.033774	.748209	.480963
$\frac{93}{60} < x < \frac{100}{60}$	0.067688	.052540	.018576	.776208	.274436
$\frac{100}{60} < x < \frac{107}{60}$	0.017028	.013135	.000000	.771371	.000000
$\frac{107}{60} < x < \frac{133}{60}$	0.028426	.013135	.000000	.462073	.000000
$\frac{133}{60} < x < \frac{140}{60}$	0.028426	.013135	.000000	.462073	.000000
$\frac{140}{60} < x < \frac{147}{60}$	0.005122	.000000	-.003715	.000000	-.725324
$\frac{147}{60} < x < \frac{173}{60}$	0.007655	.000000	-.006755	.000000	-.882397
$\frac{173}{60} < x < \frac{180}{60}$	0.006743	.000000	-.003715	.000000	-.550943
$\int_0^3 f(x) dx$	0.181272	0.152582	0.088326	0.841728	0.487257
$\int_0^\infty f(x) dx$	0.199375	0.165058	0.089392	0.827877	0.448361

Table 2a

obstructed pupil $\lambda 444 \text{ nm}$

12.5

X_{max}	E_0	$2E_1$	$2E_2$	M_1	M_2	σ_0	σ_0'
0	0	0	0	—	—	∞	∞
13/60	.029401	.026822	.021953	.912282	.746678	4.349479	7.156868
20/60	.042572	.041264	.028454	.969275	.668377	3.996297	5.770051
27/60	.052789	.053083	.033561	1.005558	.635746	3.710614	5.055536
53/60	.102923	.096980	.068044	.942253	.661113	2.625973	3.827785
60/60	.115091	.108798	.073150	.945323	.635585	2.576382	3.642269
67/60	.120624	.114928	.075317	.952779	.624399	2.550761	3.544356
97/60	.151053	.137695	.089953	.911569	.595505	2.416914	3.345074
100/60	.158950	.143825	.092120	.904844	.579554	2.418086	3.303751
107/60	.160937	.145357	.092120	.903197	.572400	2.429890	3.297567
133/60	.173255	.151049	.092120	.871834	.531704	2.517502	3.339109
140/60	.176571	.152582	.092120	.864138	.521717	2.538784	3.348390
147/60	.177168	.152582	.091687	.861223	.517511	2.553374	3.347490
173/60	.180486	.152582	.088759	.845395	.491781	2.645590	3.419410
180/60	.181272	.152582	.088326	.841728	.487257	2.661923	3.431985
∞	.199375	.165058	.089392	.827877	.448361	2.704962	3.369727

Results, in terms of light collection efficiency and astrometric weight ($\propto \sigma_0^{-2}$), are given in Fig. 5 below. The curves are qualitatively similar as in Fig. 2 (unobscured) pupil, but the "super efficiency" for a limited oversizing factor ($\beta = 1$ to 3) is even more pronounced.

4. Effect of polychromatism

(14)

We test the sensitivity of the effect observed in the previous section to a variation of wavelength by recomputing the results for a different wavelength. Assume for instance $\lambda = 533 \text{ nm}$, which gives $\lambda/s = 0.8 D/2$. The modified $F(x, \lambda)$ diagram is shown below (Fig. 6). A plot of $E_2(\beta)/E_1(\lambda)$ and relative astigmatic weight $[\sigma_0(\beta)/\sigma_0(\lambda)]^{-2}$ versus overfocusing β (Fig. 7) shows curves similar to those in Figs. 2 and 5 although the "superefficiency" is less pronounced. It can be concluded, however, that introducing polychromatism will not drastically change the results in Fig. 5 (for $\lambda \neq \lambda_{\text{eff}}$).

$ x $	$E_0(x)$	$2E_1(x)$	$2E_2(x)$	$M_1(x)$	$M_2(x)$
0 - 0.2	.135696	.123793	.101321	.912286	.746676
0.2 - 0.35	.085036	.061897	0	.727889	0
0.35 - 0.45	.062238	.061897	0	.994521	0
0.45 - 0.6	.090363	.061897	0	.684982	0
0.6 - 1.0	.115694	.101301	.079577	.875598	.687827
1.0 - 1.15	.053194	.039405	0	.740773	0
1.15 - 1.25	.041795	.039405	0	.942816	0
1.25 - 1.40	.064592	.039405	0	.610060	0
1.40 - 1.80	.070221	.052540	.033774	.748203	.480963
$\int_0^{1.8} f(x) dx$	.155886	.126816	.065605	.813516	.420850
$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) dx$	.199375	.148552	.063662	.745088	.319308

$ x _{max}$	E_0	$2E_1$	$2E_2$	M_1	M_2	σ_0	σ_0'
0.6	.059673	.049577	.020264	.829815	.339588	5.735823	6.356799
1.0	.105950	.090038	.052095	.849810	.491692	3.446405	4.439883
1.4	.127798	.105800	.052095	.827868	.407636	3.581893	4.263813
1.8	.155886	.126816	.065605	.813516	.420850	3.208365	3.912386
∞	.199375	.148552	.063662	.745088	.319308	3.431280	3.896737

5. Effect of defocusing

Introducing a wavefront aberration $\varphi(x, y)$ we have

$$t(x, y) = e^{-ik\varphi(x, y)} \quad (30)$$

and hence

$$F(x, \xi) = \int e^{-ik[\varphi(x, y) - \varphi(x+\xi, y)]} dy \quad (31)$$

A defocusing by a distance d along the optical axis corresponds to the parabolic wavefront error

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{d}{2f^2} (x^2 + y^2), \quad (32)$$

where f is the equivalent focal length. Thus (31) becomes

$$F(x, \xi) = F_0(x, \xi) e^{ikd\xi(2x+\xi)/2f^2} \quad (33)$$

where $F_0(x, \xi)$ is the corresponding function for the aberration-free telescope. We find, quite generally, (all kinds of aberrations)

$$F(x+\xi, -\xi) \equiv F^*(x, \xi), \quad (34)$$

so that the l :th ^(pair of) complex harmonic, eq. (15), becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E_l(x) &= \sum_n c_n c_{n-l} F\left(x - \frac{n\lambda}{s}, \frac{l\lambda}{s}\right); \\ E_{-l}(x) &= \sum_{n'} c_{n'} c_{n'+l} F\left(x - \frac{n'\lambda}{s}, -\frac{l\lambda}{s}\right) = \sum_n c_{n-l} c_n F\left(x - \frac{n\lambda}{s} + \frac{l\lambda}{s}, -\frac{l\lambda}{s}\right) = \\ &= \sum_n c_n c_{n-l} F^*\left(x - \frac{n\lambda}{s}, \frac{l\lambda}{s}\right) = E_l^*(x) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

(using the substitution $n \equiv n'+l$). The l :th harmonic of the intensity variation thus becomes ($l \neq 0$) [eq. (12)]:

$$I_l(x) \equiv E_l(x) e^{-i2\pi l p_0/s} + E_l^*(x) e^{i2\pi l p_0/s} =$$

$$I_E(x) = 2 \cos \left[\frac{2\pi l p_0}{s} - \arg(E_E(x)) \right]. \quad (36) \quad (18)$$

Thus, the displacement (on the focal surface) corresponding to the argument of $E_E(x)$ is

$$p_0(x; l) = \frac{s}{2\pi l} \arg[E_E(x)]. \quad (37)$$

Inserting (33) into (15) we find

$$\begin{aligned} E_E(x) &= \sum_n c_n c_{n-l} F_0 \left(x - \frac{n\lambda}{s}, \frac{l\lambda}{s} \right) e^{ikd \frac{l\lambda}{s} \left(2x - \frac{2n\lambda}{s} + \frac{l\lambda}{s} \right) / 2f^2} \\ &= e^{ikd l\lambda x / sf^2} e^{ikd (l\lambda/s)^2 / 2f^2} \sum_n c_n c_{n-l} F_0(\cdot) e^{-ikd \frac{l\lambda}{s} \frac{n\lambda}{s} / f^2} \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The exponential in the summation, $e^{-ikd \frac{l\lambda}{s} \frac{n\lambda}{s} / f^2}$, will introduce phase shifts of the harmonics, and also a decreased amplitude, if more than one term (m) contributes to the sum. The second exponential in (38), $e^{ikd (l\lambda/s)^2 / 2f^2}$, is a constant shift (independent of x), amounting to

$$p_{00} = \frac{s}{2\pi l} \frac{2\pi d l^2 \lambda^2}{\lambda s^2 \cdot 2f^2} = \frac{l\lambda d}{2sf^2} \quad (\text{radians}) \quad (39)$$

The first ~~two~~ exponential factor, is the only one which depends on x , i.e. the position in the relay-optics collecting lens. It corresponds to the shift

$$p_0(x) = \frac{s}{2\pi l} \frac{k d l \lambda x}{sf^2} = x d / f^2. \quad (40)$$

It is important to note that this shift is achromatic and independent of l . However, since it depends on x , there

will be two effects to consider:

- (1) due to the integration (by the collecting lens) over x , there will be a decreased modulation, viz. if $p_0(x_{max})$ is substantial (compared with s);
- (2) the effective shift of the collected light, due to $p_0(x)$, is obtained (approximately) as the intensity-weighted average of x over the collecting interval $x \in [x_1, x_2]$. If x_1 and x_2 (the boundaries of the collecting lens) are shifted by Δx , the change in $p_0(x)$ will be, at most, of the order of $\Delta x \cdot d / f^2$.

Taking $f = 2.5 \text{ m}$ and $d = 5 \mu\text{m}$ as a typical defocusing, and $x_{max} = 2.5 \text{ cm}$, we have $p_0 = l \lambda d / 2s f^2 \approx 3 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ rad} = 0.007 \text{ l}$ and $x d / f^2 = 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ rad} = 0.004$. This is negligible compared with s and thus does not cause a degradation of modulation (there is a degradation, of course, due to the exponential terms in the sum over n).

Realistically, $|\Delta x| \ll 1 \text{ mm} \Rightarrow |\Delta x d / f^2| \ll 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ arcsec}$.

Conclusion: defocusing in combination with non-centred relay optics cannot produce significant apparent image displacements.